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ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

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INTERNATIONAL LEGAL MECHANISM FOR MONITORING DRUG TRAFFICKING

ANNOTATION

The author raises the problem of international cooperation between states in the field of illegal circulation of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances. References are given to the main, signed in different years, conventions concerning this problem. The general principles of combating crime developed by the United Nations are considered. The historical experience of combating crime is analyzed. It is noted that the UN congresses on the prevention of crime and the treatment of offenders play a special role in preventing and combating transnational organized crime. Analyzed the main international normative legal acts in this area.

Key words: United Nations, transnational crime, illicit trafficking in narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances and precursors, directions of international cooperation, control measures, control measures.

ГИЁХВАНДЛИК ВОСИТАЛАРНИ МУОМАЛАСИНИ НАЗОРАТ ҚИЛИШНИНГ ХАЛҚАРО-ҲУҚУҚИЙ МЕХАНИЗМИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Муаллиф гиёҳвандлик воситалари ва психотроп моддаларнинг ноқонуний муомаласи соҳасида давлатлар ўртасидаги халқаро ҳамкорлик муаммосини кўтаради. Ушбу муаммо билан боғлиқ турли йилларда имзоланган асосий конвенцияларга ҳаволалар берилган. Бирлашган Миллатлар Ташкилоти томонидан ишлаб чиқилган жиноятчиликка қарши курашнинг умумий тамойиллари кўриб чиқилган. Жиноятчиликка қарши курашнинг тарихий тажрибаси таҳлил қилинган. Трансмиллий уюшган жиноятчиликнинг олдини олиш ва унга қарши курашишда БМТнинг жиноятчиликнинг олдини олиш ва ҳуқуқбузарларга қарши курашиш бўйича конгресслари алоҳида ўрин тутган. Бу борадаги асосий халқаро норматив-ҳуқуқий ҳужжатларни таҳлил қилинган.

Калит сўзлар: Бирлашган Миллатлар Ташкилоти, трансмиллий жиноятчилик, гиёҳвандлик воситалари, психотроп моддалар ва прекурсорларнинг ноқонуний айланиши, халқаро ҳамкорлик йўналишлари, назорат чоралари, қарши курашиш чоралари.

МЕЖДУНАРОДНО-ПРАВОВОЙ МЕХАНИЗМ КОНТРОЛЯ ЗА ОБОРОТОМ НАРКОТИЧЕСКИХ СРЕДСТВ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Автор поднимает проблему международного сотрудничества государств в сфере незаконного оборота наркотических средств и психотропных веществ. Даны ссылки на основные, подписанные в разные годы, конвенции, касающиеся данной проблемы. Рассматриваются общие принципы борьбы с преступностью, выработанные Организацией Объединенных Наций. Анализируется исторический опыт противодействия преступности. Отмечается, что особую роль в вопросах предупреждения транснациональной организованной преступности и борьбы с ней играют конгрессы ООН по предупреждению преступности и обращению с правонарушителями. Проанализированы основные международные нормативно-правовые акты в указанной сфере.

Ключевые слова: Организация Объединенных Наций, транснациональное преступление, незаконный оборот наркотических средств, психотропных веществ и прекурсоров, направления международного сотрудничества, меры борьбы, меры контроля.

In 2015, the United Nations celebrated 70 years since its inception. The Organization celebrates its jubilee in difficult conditions caused by both international events of the last decade and internal organizational problems. At the same time, over the past years, the UN has become the largest and most authoritative international organization, spreading its influence on various spheres of public life, covering and leading the solution of global problems of all mankind. Among such problems, which as a potential and obvious threat affect every state of the world, special attention is given to the problem of illicit trafficking in drugs and psychotropic substances.

Today, the United Nations Organization has significant experience in coordinating cooperation between states and lawmaking in the field of combating drug trafficking. For the first time within the framework of the Organization, the problem of drug trafficking was raised in the middle of the 50s of the XX century, when the ineffectiveness of previously adopted international agreements in this area became clear [1].

A fairly large number of narcotic drugs and drug-containing preparations, as well as the raw materials that were used in their manufacture, remained outside the international legal regulation. In addition, a number of provisions of the international agreements in force have become outdated, while the rapid growth of the illegal drug trade has become a serious problem for some countries.

In this regard, under the auspices of the United Nations, a number of conventions were developed and subsequently adopted, aimed at correcting certain provisions of previously existing acts. With the conclusion of the 1961 Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs [2], which replaced the earlier documents (with the exception of the 1936 Convention), the scope of international control was unified and expanded. The main purpose of the 1961 Convention, enshrined by the parties to the treaty in its preamble, was to restrict the use of narcotic drugs exclusively for medical and scientific purposes.

The single convention consists of 51 articles and four lists of narcotic drugs, distributed depending on the established control regime. All substances on these lists are traded and distributed only under licenses. The parties to the agreement are encouraged to recognize as punishable all actions committed with the substances specified in the lists in violation of the provisions of the Convention.

The Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs seeks to restrict the production, distribution and use of drugs, as well as the possession and trade of drugs exclusively in the field of medicine and scientific purposes.

In addition, the Convention invites States parties to introduce special measures for specific drugs, such as heroin. The 1972 Protocol adopted to this Convention focuses on the need for treatment and rehabilitation of drug addicts.

The most stringent control measures have been established for substances listed in list I. These include preparations obtained from the opium poppy, coca bush leaves, and hemp. Schedule II contains prescription drugs commonly used in the practice. Schedule III lists preparations that include substances from Schedule II in low concentrations. List IV includes narcotic drugs that are used in limited quantities for medical purposes and the circulation of which, at the discretion of the parties to the agreement, can be completely prohibited.

As new drug-containing drugs appear, the lists are updated (Article 3) and supplemented. One or another drug can be added to any of the lists upon the submission of one of the participating countries or the World Health Organization (WHO). According to the Convention, the states parties to the treaty have reduced the number of international drug control bodies and entrusted it to the Commission on Narcotic Drugs (CND) of the UN Economic and Social Council and the International Narcotics Control Board (INCB).

By the time the Single Convention was adopted, international drug control was exercised by 4 bodies: the Commission on Narcotic Drugs, the Permanent Central Opium Committee, the Narcotic Drugs Control Authority, the Expert Committee on Toxicogenic Drugs at the World Health Organization [3].

It should be noted that the reporting system of states provided for by the 1961 Convention is quite complex and includes a large amount of information regarding the geography and area of growth of drug-containing plants, the amount of drugs produced and consumed, their stocks, as well as enterprises employed in production (Art Articles 19, 20).

The signatory countries undertake the obligation to submit to the UN Secretary-General annually reports on the application of the Convention in their territories and the texts of all laws and regulations relating to narcotic substances, as well as to provide the names and addresses of organizations issuing export permits or certificates for the import of drugs. and statistics on drugs. An important instrument of international control, through which the import and export of drugs is limited, are the estimates of the requirements for narcotic drugs, which states also submit to the International Narcotics Control Board.

In Art. 4 of the Single Convention states that the import and export of narcotic drugs should be limited exclusively to medical and scientific purposes. Art. 36 of the Convention speaks of the punishability of the import and export of narcotic drugs in violation of the provisions of the convention. Thus, the concepts of "import" and "export" are introduced into the text of the Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs, which, in accordance with Art. 1 of this document "means, in their respective semantic shades, the physical movement of drugs from one state to another state or from one territory to another territory of the same state".

In other words, any movement of narcotic drugs, regardless of the fact of crossing the state border, is considered their import or export. In the opinion of individual authors [4], an attempt to combine by one concept the actions associated with the cross-border transportation of drugs and their movement within the country can hardly be called the most successful, if only because these actions are of a different order. For example, the movement of drugs from the territory of one state to the territory of another in violation of the provisions of this convention can be classified as an international crime, while their illegal movement within the country is not such. Accordingly, the degree and nature of the consequences of these acts, their legal assessment in national legislation, are different.

It seems that it would be more logical to define each action independently and designate the movement of drugs from one state to another, for example, with the concepts of "export" and "import". In addition to these provisions, the Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs contains a large number of other important aspects. At the same time, it is necessary to note the points that were not taken into account in the development of the document.

Thus, the control established by the 1961 Convention applies only to narcotic drugs and does not affect the trade in psychotropic substances, which has been rapidly expanding in many countries. By the early 1970s, the spread of stimulants was becoming a big threat and uncontrollable. The need to establish control aimed at preventing the abuse of psychotropic substances led to the adoption in 1971 of the Convention on Psychotropic Substances [5].

By analogy with the Single Convention, this Convention contains four lists of substances. List 1 includes psychotropic substances with especially dangerous hallucinogenic properties. It is noteworthy that more stringent control measures are envisaged for these substances (Article 7) than those applied to narcotic substances included in List 1 of the 1961 Convention (Article 31). Their use is completely prohibited, except for scientific and extremely narrow medical purposes. Schedule II lists stimulants of very limited therapeutic value.

Schedule III contains substances that are widely used for medical purposes and are abused. List IV includes drugs with hypnotic, tranquilizing and analgesic effects. As in the case of narcotic drugs, a licensed system of trade in psychotropic substances is introduced (Articles 8.12). In Art. Twenty-two states have undertaken to make willful acts committed in violation of the provisions of this Convention punishable. Meanwhile, unlike the Single Convention, there is no specific list of such acts.

When individuals travel from one country to another, the Convention allows them to carry a small amount of psychotropic drugs for personal use, but the countries parties to the Convention are given the right to make sure that the drugs are obtained legally. One of the features of the 1971 Convention can be attributed to the fact that considerable attention is paid to the development of national legislation aimed at preventing and suppressing illicit trafficking in psychotropic substances (Articles 20, 21, 23).

This is due to the fact that, in contrast to the illicit trafficking of narcotic drugs obtained in the course of illegal (clandestine) production, psychotropic substances enter illicit trafficking, mainly through their diversion from legal traffic. In these conditions, the absence in some countries-producers (exporters) of psychotropic substances of the relevant legislation establishing strict control over the distribution of such substances, significantly complicates the possibility of their use only for medical and scientific purposes and leads to the abuse of these substances.

Therefore, the 1971 Convention establishes a strict requirement for states parties to take in their domestic legislation all measures to prevent the diversion of psychotropic substances from legal to illegal traffic. International norms emphasize the responsibility of states for non-compliance with this requirement and provide for the possibility of applying sanctions to those states that do not enshrine in their legislation a system of strict control over the production and distribution of psychotropic substances. However, the forms of such sanctions are not determined by the Convention, which somewhat reduces the effectiveness of this peremptory norm [4].

This document occupies an important place in the regulation of international traffic in psychotropic substances. However, the scale of illegal drug trafficking continued to expand in the 1970s and 1980s, and the control established by the 1961 and 1971 Conventions turned out to be inadequate to the problem.

In this regard, in its resolution 39/41 of December 14, 1984, the UN General Assembly recognized that "the enormous scale of drug trafficking and its consequences urgently require the preparation of a convention that would cover all the various aspects of the problem, and especially those that are not provided by the relevant international legal instruments". The result of work in this direction was the UN Convention against Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances [6], adopted at a conference in Vienna in December 1988.

Its participants noted the trend of growth in "illegal production, demand and turnover of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances", as well as the fact that children often become consumers of the potion. In the preamble to the treaty, its participants note that the availability of these substances is also one of the reasons for the growth in the illegal production of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances [7].

The convention is a framework agreement for international cooperation in the fight against drug trafficking. Its members made a commitment to eradicate or reduce the demand for drugs. The Vienna Convention covers a wide range of issues related to the functioning of the international drug control system.

It defines a comprehensive set of measures to combat drug trafficking, including provisions against money laundering and diversion of parent chemicals. It also provides for the discovery, freezing and confiscation of income and property obtained from drug trafficking, the extradition of drug couriers and the initiation of criminal cases.

The convention has expanded the list of offenses related to drugs and psychotropic substances. In particular, member states may criminalize "the production, extraction, preparation, offer, offer for the purpose of sale, distribution, sale, supply under any conditions, mediation, transfer, transit, transportation, import or export of any drug or any psychotropic substance "; cultivation of opium poppy, coca bush or cannabis; manufacturing, transportation or distribution of equipment, materials or substances intended for the cultivation, production or manufacture of drugs or psychotropic substances.

The countries that have signed this Convention are invited to amend their legislation so that courts considering offenses involving drugs and psychotropic substances can take into account as aggravating circumstances the group nature of the crime, the participation of the accused in other crimes or in the activities of an international criminal group, the use of violence or weapons involving minors.

Each member state sets the statute of limitations for such crimes independently. The parties to the Convention are also given the right to independently develop measures necessary for the confiscation of proceeds from illegal activities with drugs, as well as the drugs themselves. The convention provides for cooperation of states in the fight against drugs, directly or through international organizations.

In addition, the 1988 UN Convention against Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances establishes the use of the terms "physical movement of a psychotropic substance from one state to another state" as a definition of export and import for any drug. In Art. 3 States parties to the Convention are encouraged to take such measures as may be necessary to criminalize the export or import of any narcotic drug or any psychotropic substance under their laws in violation of the 1961 (amended), 1971 Conventions and 1988 year

A characteristic feature of this convention is that it reflects the desire of states to jointly suppress criminal activities related to drug trafficking by addressing the root causes of drug abuse, including the illicit demand for them and the huge profits generated from the sale of drugs. This is undoubtedly an indicator of the serious attention of the parties to the agreement to the transnational scale of the drug trade.

In addition to the specialized conventions of the United Nations, which are entirely aimed at combating drug trafficking, the provisions of some other universal acts, the regulation of which are aimed at completely different spheres of interstate relations, meet similar goals and objectives. For example, the operation of the above UN Conventions of 1961, 1971, and 1988 is supplemented by the application of the provisions of the International Convention on Mutual Administrative Assistance in the Prevention, Investigation and Suppression of Customs Offenses of 1977, or rather its Annex X "Assistance in the fight against smuggling of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances "[8].

This international legal act is of interest in relation to the definition of "smuggling of drugs and psychotropic substances" enshrined in it. In accordance with Art. 1 (d) "smuggling of drugs and psychotropic substances" means "deception of customs, consisting in the movement of drugs and psychotropic substances across the customs border in any hidden form." The term "customs cheating" means "a customs offense in which a person deceives customs and thus partially or completely avoids paying import or export duties and taxes, or bypasses bans or restrictions established by customs legislation, or obtains other benefits in violation of customs legislation."

In addition, this Convention calls on the States parties to consider offenses related to drug smuggling only in the context of the 1961 United Nations Convention. substances, etc. In addition to international acts that are binding, imperative for the participating States, the United Nations has adopted many acts of a recommendatory nature, which, while not having a binding force, nevertheless, are an important component of the universal international legal mechanism for combating illicit drug trafficking and psychotropic drugs. substances.

First of all, it is important to note the significant role of the UN General Assembly. So, in its resolution of February 23, 1990 at the 17th special session of the UN General Assembly, it adopted the Political Declaration and the World Program of Action in the field of international cooperation against illicit production, supply, demand, circulation and distribution of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances [9].

The World Program of Action has become a document that accumulates a detailed and comprehensive list of measures, the joint and coordinated implementation of which will allow states to move forward in solving this global problem. Continuous monitoring of the implementation of the World Program of Action in accordance with paragraph 97 is entrusted to the UN Commission on Narcotic Drugs. To assist the Commission in this, more than 60 governments have provided information to the UN Board on Narcotic Drugs on activities to implement the World Program of Action.

The General Assembly has been actively working in the past few years as well. At the same time, the UN General Assembly seeks to cover all aspects of drug trafficking. Thus, considerable attention is paid to the problem of combating the legalization of proceeds from drug trafficking. At its regular session on October 22, 1997, the General Assembly called on all states to apply the provisions of the 1988 UN Convention against Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances aimed at curbing money laundering.

One of the results of the XX Special Session of the UN General Assembly held in June 1998 in New York was the adoption by the UN member states of the Political Declaration and the Declaration on Guiding Principles for Drug Demand Reduction [10].

Although the provisions of the Declaration on the Guiding Principles for Drug Demand Reduction cover mainly the area of prevention and focus on drug demand reduction, their application forms an integral part of the international strategy to combat the smuggling of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances. The world community recognizes that it is necessary to make active efforts both in the direction of suppressing the illicit production and distribution of drugs, and in the prevention of their abuse.

Unlike the previous document, the Political Declaration is aimed at solving the drug problem [11] in general. Its significance lies in the fact that through this document it was possible to draw the attention of governments to new trends in the field of drug trafficking. In particular, the declaration reflected the reaction of the participants in the special session of the UN General Assembly to the rapid growth of illegal export and import of synthetic drugs.

Undoubtedly, the international legal mechanism for combating the drug threat created under the auspices of the United Nations will continue to improve in the future, since the need for a more comprehensive approach to the problem is obvious, and therefore deeper integration in issues of interaction, which only the UN can provide. In particular, the analysis makes it possible to propose to formulate within the UN framework a special institutional mechanism for coordinating the activities of regional organizations to counter the drug threat.

In conclusion, it can be noted that thanks to the adoption of the universal international drug control treaties, it was possible to achieve a reduction in the manufacture and trade of many controlled substances. The universal international legal mechanism created to date, supplemented by the action of the appropriate national legal means, makes it possible in a sufficiently effective form to counteract the illicit distribution of drugs on a global scale.

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11. The “drug problem” in the declaration refers to the illicit cultivation, production, manufacture, sale, demand, trafficking and distribution of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances, including amphetamine-type stimulants and precursors, as well as related criminal activities.

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